

Research Data Management and Processing for an Irish Geoscience Research Centre and its Stakeholders

Burbidge C¹, Melo A¹, Torremans K¹

¹iCRAG, University College Dublin

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT AND PROCESSING FOR iCRAG & STAKEHOLDERS

Burbidge, C.I.^{*1}, Melo, A.¹ and Torremans, K.¹

¹iCRAG SFI Centre for Research in Applied Geosciences, School of Earth Sciences, University College Dublin, Ireland

^{*}presenting author (email: christopher.burbidge@icrag-centre.org)

FAIR, Open, Irish_Geodata, Enterprise_Architecture, Data_Strategy

1 INTRODUCTION

Established in 2015, iCRAG is the world leading Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre in applied geosciences hosted by UCD. It comprises 150 researchers across eight universities and institutions, with a total of 34 industry, policy and research partner organisations. iCRAG2 aims to deliver more extensive, integrated research on the earth system to facilitate environmentally sustainable development of the earth resources required for decarbonized economies, and to promote understanding of how people react to and manage our relationship with the earth. iCRAG is at the heart of Irish geoscience data: public and commercial; use and production; transformation and processing; recovery and storage. Therefore, iCRAG is ideally suited to the role of Aggregator for Irish geoscience data, in partnership with HEAnet, UCD Research IT, and the Geological Survey of Ireland National Geoscience Datacentre.

UN sustainable development goals on FAIR data and Open science are informing EU directives, national governmental policy, and so the strategy of iCRAG's funding and IT focussed infrastructure agencies, SFI and HEAnet. FAIR data may be equated with being machine readable, since then it is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The revised Group on Earth Observations (GEO) data sharing Data Sharing and Data Management Principles detail key data management principles for the geosciences. The Geological Survey of Ireland National Geoscience Datacentre is Ireland's geodata archive. FAIR data facilitates Open Science. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Ireland's National Open Research Forum are driving open research, Ireland does not yet have its own EUDAT node.

Cloud ICT and service based infrastructure development would have a transformative effect on the scope and scale of iCRAG2 data management policy, technological platforms and targeted project areas, but needs to be developed and resourced. The objectives of the current work are to develop planning, partnering, and proposals for iCRAG data. These are focussed on helping develop FAIR Open Geoscience data provision for Ireland and beyond, helping Ireland towards full engagement with the European Open Science Cloud and EUDAT, developing iCRAG data management policies, and preparing data strategy for iCRAG3. SFI interests include development of iCRAG's intranet and EOSC engagement.

2 METHODOLOGY

A basis of developing fair and open data management and processing is setting up equitable and sustainable access. This was begun by consultation with iCRAG researchers and staff, to learn their data needs and to identify selected analytical problems to help solve and implement. This helped develop understanding of the software packages, operating systems and platforms used, and those of interest, as well as current engagement with open source systems and applications, coding and centralised computing resources. Based on this and taking into account long term staffing and licensing, a pilot generalised open source operating and applications ecosystem was selected, installed and tested for desktop use. This was designed to be a foundation for diverse individual research setups. It focussed on GIS and databasing geodata, plus office work. As planning for centralised data management and processing developed to consider infrastructure for visualisation, compute, and data warehouse / lake nodes, compatible applications for data management and administration were identified and set up on a dedicated iCRAG server and EUDAT platforms were investigated. This was combined with the iCRAG2 project plan to map iCRAG applications and Enterprise Architecture.

To enable the development and implementation of iCRAG's strategic data objectives, the iCRAG data use case has been included in the IRLDAT project and forms the basis of the GEOSCI proposal to EOSC-Future. IRLDAT is led by HEAnet in partnership with Irish RITs and ICHEC. It is developing a pilot for national research data infrastructure, leading towards an EUDAT node for Ireland. GEOSCI is an iCRAG led proposal for EU resourcing of commercial cloud "Infrastructure as a Service plus" aspects of Platform and Software. It is designed to aggregate our community's engagement with EOSC. To develop this, active community participation on research data management by the authors includes the iCRAG-HEAnet focus group and membership of UCD Research Data Management community hosted by UCD Library. We participated in the Group on Earth Observations Data Sharing and Data Management dialogues series, and are a member of the Research

Data Alliance working group on Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes (Repo2Pub). iCRAG colleagues are active in NORF working groups.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The tested open source operating system and applications ecosystem is run on Ubuntu with LibreOffice and Mozilla office suite, with Jupyter notebook in Anaconda, and QGIS with GRASS plugins and GRASS GIS linked to a PostGre+PostGIS database via pgAdmin. Identified data management packages are Apache NiFi. The iCRAG business architecture diagram (Figure 2) shows how different research project and user needs map to resources being developed in IRLDAT and for EOSC Future. These feed into the national geoscience datacentre, and through them iCRAG will develop experience and integration with central data management and computing initiatives. The iCRAG applications architecture diagram (Figure 3) indicates how this can be done using what software. EUDAT applications focus on convenient file-based data management, while associated functionality could form the basis of an intranet. EOSC IaaS+ is focussed on supporting the complementary areas of datawarehouse development and accessible high performance geoscience computation. These are live diagrams that are evolving as consultation, detailed planning and project activities advance.

Figure 1: GEOSci context in strategic initiatives, policy frameworks and proposals

Figure 2: Conceptual Business Architecture for iCRAG in EOSC Future and IRLDAT

Figure 3: Conceptual Applications Architecture for iCRAG in EOSC Future and IRLDAT

4 CONCLUSIONS

iCRAG is building engagement in national, EU and international data management initiatives on modern cloud service based research data management and data archiving. Alignment with institutional and funding agency strategies has built support to resource the development of fair and open solutions. Targeted proposals have been developed through business unit led Enterprise Architecture planning in close collaboration with IT management and commercial suppliers. Practical architectures are enabling a multi institution SFI research centre to address the challenge of building data management mechanisms between legal entities to improve access to Irish Geoscience resources and data: for current research and into the future.

Through the initiatives developed in this work, iCRAG will provide and develop:

- Cloud infrastructure for the Irish geoscience research community;
- Order of magnitude increase in accessible and usable Irish geoscience data;
- Multi-institution, national coverage by stakeholders;
- New FAIR systems for geoscience data management for Ireland;
- Upscaling from local to national geological and geophysical rendering and modelling;
- Alignment with institutional research IT infrastructure developments, providing a case study;
- Helping GSI deliver Ireland's National Geoscience Datacentre;
- Facilitate iCRAG data management policy and develop data strategy for iCRAG3.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This presentation has emanated from research supported in part by a research grant from Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) under Grant Number R18462, and collaboration with partners HEAnet, UCED RIT and the National Open Research Forum (NORF) which is supported by the Government of Ireland through the Higher Education Authority.